

GENERALIZED WATER SUPPLY SYSTEM IN VILLAGES

Ustemirov Shokhrukh Rustam Ugli¹

¹ Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4968735>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 05th June 2021

Accepted: 10th June 2021

Online: 15th June 2021

KEY WORDS

drinking water, water supply system, generalized, trunk water, economically, technical equipment, pumping units.

ABSTRACT

It is desirable to overthrow the generalized water supply system in villages where there is no source of drinking water. That is, water is supplied from the water source to dozens of villages located on the ridge through a single trunk water intake pipeline. In some cases, the self-sufficiency of such a trunk water transmission pipeline can reach 30-40 km and even more. Therefore, in such cases, it is desirable to divide the trunk water transmission pipe into several separate sections by water-retaining capacities (reservoirs) and pumping units.

We are all well aware that the provision of clean drinking water to the population is becoming an urgent issue for all countries today. A lot of work is being done in this direction under the leadership of the president of our republic. The implementation of the rural water supply system at the level of today's requirements requires great experience and qualification from engineer designers and builders. There are many technical literature, guidelines and jurisprudents on the design and construction of a municipal water supply system. But technical literature and recommendations on the rural water supply system although there will be no. For this reason, a group of scientists from the Samarkand State Institute of architecture and construction and Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute have been conducting scientific research on this issue for several years. We will dwell on some of the results of this work in this article.

It is desirable to overthrow the generalized water supply system in villages where there is no source of drinking water. That is, water is supplied from the water source to dozens of villages located on the ridge through a single trunk water intake pipeline. In some cases, the self-sufficiency of such a trunk water transmission pipeline can reach 30-40 km and even more. Therefore, in such cases, the collapse of the national water supply network does not correspond to the economic crisis. When water is absorbed into dozens of villages through a single trunk water transmission pipeline, the working pressure in the pipeline is very high, which leads to inconvenience both economically and in the use of technical equipment. Therefore, in such cases, it is desirable to divide the trunk water transmission pipe into several separate sections by water-retaining capacities (reservoirs) and pumping units.

We recommend that you use water pumps that are sanded in water to drive water away, that is, deliver water to consumers. As a result, it will not be necessary to build a building in olokhida for the pumping station and heat it in autumn and winter. On the basis of the above-mentioned recommendations, the project, in which the water supply system of 20 villages belonging to the meeting of citizens of Polatchi village in Pakhtachi District of Samarkand region was used, was developed by the authors in 2008, was built and launched by the engineering company of the Samarkand region municipality at the beginning of 2009. As a source of water for the project, the main water supply pipeline "Damkhoja-Bukhoro" was purchased. The total length of the summarized trunk water intake pipeline was 18.5 km. Two pumping stations were built on the basis of the project for water transmission. The first water-lifting pump station "Damkhoja-Buxoro" was built next to the main water transmission pipeline. The second was built after 10 villages. For water storage, two 50 m³, one 10 m³ capacity (reservoir) were built, and four water-submersible pumps were installed. Polyethylene pipes were

used for the generalized water absorption trunk pipeline. The diameter of the pipe at the initial plots of the trunk water intake pipe was 200 mm, at the last plots was 63 mm.

Water is supplied to 20 villages owned by the Polatchi village Citizens Assembly through a water supply system that has been generalized for 3 years. At the same time, the state of all devices, equipment, pumps and pipes in the water supply system is constantly being studied by the authors.

Often, several villages are served by a single generalized water supply system. For example, drinking water is supplied to several villages through water transmission networks, 2 with the help of pumps located "A" (picture - 1) in the water intake facility. In connection with the fact that the distance between the villages is quite long, the length of the water transmission network can be tens of kilometres. Therefore, at the 2 starting point of the water network, the pezometric elevation height of the water "A" will be much larger than the "B" at its end point, that is, $H_a > H_b$. In such cases, it is desirable to distribute water through pressure gauges from the 2 initial part of the water supply pipes to the 3/4 length part.

Picture -1

1-water intake facility, 2-water transmission pipeline, 3-villages, 4-water distribution network.

2 from the water supply pipes it is convenient to give each village through a separate water distribution network through a water meter. Firstly, if conditions

are created to give water to a each village on a graphical basis, and secondly, the each village is easier to knit by regulating the

working pressure in the water distribution networks.

Currently, polyethylene pipes are used for almost all water transmission networks. When choosing polyethylene pipes, great attention should be paid to the working pressure that is formed in the water transmission pipes. If polyethylene pipes are used at high pressure for a short period of time, that is, if they are used at high pressure above the intended pressure, then the polyethylene pipes will quickly run out of work, and the service life will be sharply reduced. For this reason, when using polyethylene pipes, it is necessary to install flanges that do not allow increased pressure in the pumps.

The graph of water consumption in villages is often changed by hours. This in turn has a negative impact on the performance of the pumps. Therefore, in the pumps used in rural water supply, a

special device should be used to keep the pressure at a norm after the pump. Observations on the operation of the pumps have shown that it is necessary to ensure that the height of the water in the water storage tanks is automatically turned off when the distance from the push part of the pump to the water level is reduced by 1 meter. It is necessary to ensure that the pumps fly automatically when changes (voltage increase or decrease) occur in the supply of electricity. As a result of the interruption of electricity or the graphic transmission of water in the villages, there will be no water left in the umulad trunk water transmission pipes, that is, the choke part of the trunk pipe will be drained. This has a negative effect on the pumps in the operation of reversing pumps. Therefore, after the pumps, it is necessary to install pressure sliders.

References:

1. Хажиматова М. М. Сооружение для забора подземных вод //Символ науки: международный научный журнал. – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
2. Устемиров Ш.Р.У. Анализ систем оборотного водоснабжения и проблем качества воды промышленных предприятий //European science. – 2020. – №. 2-2 (51).
3. Махмудова Д. Э., Мусаев Ш. М. Воздействие промышленных загрязнителей на окружающую среду //Академическая публицистика. – 2020. – №. 12. – С. 76-83.
4. Хажиматова М. М., Саттаров А. Экологик таълимни ривожлантиришда инновация жараёнлари //Ме'мorchilik va qarilish muammolari. – 2019. – С. 48.
5. Sultonov A. et al. Pollutant Standards for Mining Enterprises. – EasyChair, 2021. – №. 5134.
6. Мусаев Ш. М. Мероприятие сокращение загрязнение атмосферы вредными веществами //Ме'мorchilik va qarilish muammolari. – 2020. – С. 45.
7. Алиев М.К., Махмудова Д.Э. Роль естественного биоценоза в процессе очистки питьевой воды //Международный научный сельскохозяйственный журнал. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 7-8.
8. Ernazarovna M. D., Sattorovich B. E. Assessment Of Water Quality Of Small Rivers Of The Syrdarya Basins For The Safe Water Use //PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology. – 2020. – Т. 17. – №. 7. – С. 9901-9910.
9. Махмудов И.Э., Махмудова Д.Э., Мурадов Н. Оценка потенциала чирчикского и ахангаранского речных бассейнов для повышения эффективности использования стока рек на территории республики узбекистана //Водосбережение, мелиорация и

- гидротехнические сооружения как основа формирования агрокультурных кластеров России в XXI веке. – 2016. – С. 251-257.
10. Мусаев Ш.М., Саттаров А. Умягчение состав воды с помощью реагентов //Me' morchilik va qurilish muammolari. – 2019. – С. 23.
 11. Такабоев К.У., Мусаев Ш.М., Хожиматова М.М. Загрязнение атмосферы вредными веществами и мероприятия их сокращение //Экология: вчера, сегодня, завтра. – 2019. – С. 450-455.
 12. Махмудова Д. Э., Кучкарова Д. Х. Методы моделирования водного режима почвы //Пути повышения эффективности орошаемого земледелия. – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 198-202.
 13. Махмудова Д. Э., Эрназаров А. Т. Изменение минерализации воды в проточных водоемах //Журнал Проблемы механики. – 2006. – №. 4. – С. 24-28.
 14. Турсунов М. К. и др. Новые инновационные методы повышения экономической эффективности при дефиците воды в регионе //Science and Education. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 78-83.
 15. Mamasolievna K. M., Mamarazhabovich M. S. the essence of the theory of gas-liquid flow and its use in solving technical problems //ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 12. – С. 1318-1322.
 16. Мирзоев А. А. Мирзоев, А. А., Ходжаев, Я. Д., Хусанов, И. Н., & Хажиматова, М. М. Многофазные среды со сложной реологией и их механические модели //XI Всероссийский съезд по фундаментальным проблемам теоретической и прикладной механики. – 2015. – С. 2558-2561.
 17. Шохрух Р.У.У. Агрокластеры как стратегия эффективного использования водных ресурсов //Science and Education. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 7.
 18. Shukurov G. et al. " Thermal conductivity of lightweight concrete depending on the moisture content of the material //International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 08. – С. 6381.
 19. Сафарова М. А. Сувни тежамкорлик билан ишлатиш ва муҳофаза қилиш ишлари //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3.
 20. Мирзоев А. А. и др. Многофазные среды со сложной реологией и их механические модели //XI Всероссийский съезд по фундаментальным проблемам теоретической и прикладной механики. – 2015. – С. 2558-2561.
 21. Мусаев Ш. М. и др. Насос агрегатларини ҳосил бўладиган гидравлик зарблардан ҳимоялаш усуллари тадқиқ этиш //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 211-220.
 22. Хажиматова М. М. Некоторые гидродинамические эффекты, проявляемые при пузырьковом и снарядном режимах течения газожидкостной смеси //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 257-264.
 23. Nazarovna A. N. Reliability and cost-effectiveness of polymer pipes //Euro-Asia Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 7-11.
 24. Алибекова Н. Н. и др. Зонирование водопроводных сетей //Science and Education. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 228-233.

25. Алибекова Н. Н. Сувдан фойдаланиш жараёнларида ахборот тизимларини қўллаш //Science and Education. – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 3.
26. Тошматов Н. У., Мансурова Ш. П. Возможности использование сточных вод заводов по переработки плодоовощных продуктов для орошения сельскохозяйственных полей //Me' morchilik va qurilish muammolari. – 2019. – С. 44.
27. Тошматов Н. У., Сайдуллаев С. Р. О методах определения потери и подсосов воздуха в вентиляционных сетях //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 7-2. – С. 72-75.
28. Ташматов Н. У., Мансурова Ш. П. Исследование воздухопроводов с продольной щелью или отверстиями и способы обеспечения равномерной раздачи или всасывания воздуха //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 200-208.
29. Сайдуллаев С. Р., Сатторов А. Б. Ананавий қозонхона ўчоқларида ёқилғи сарфини таҳлил қилиш ва камчиликларини бартараф этиш //Научно-методический журнал "Uz Akademia. – 2020. – С. 198-204.
30. Турсунов М. К., Улугбеков Б. Б. Оптимизация размещения солнечных коллекторов на ограниченной площади //Me' morchilik va qurilish muammolari. – 2020. – Т. 56.
31. Karimovich T. M., Obidovich S. A. To increase the effectiveness of the use of Information Systems in the use of water //Development issues of innovative economy in the agricultural sector. – 2021. – С.222-225.
32. Ergashev R. R., Xolbutayev B. T. Change in level water in pumping-plant intake //Irrigation and Melioration. – 2020. – Т. 2020. – №. 3. – С. 36-38.
33. Ergashev R. et al. New methods for geoinformation systems of tests and analysis of causes of failure elements of pumping stations //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2020. – Т. 883. – №. 1. – С. 012015.
34. Rashidov J., Kholbutayev B. Water distribution on machine canals trace cascade of pumping stations //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2020. – Т. 883. – №. 1. – С. 012066.
35. Кутлимуродов У. М. Некоторые аспекты экологических проблем, связанные с автомобильными транспортом //European Scientific Conference. – 2020. – С. 50-52.
36. Кутлимуродов У. М. Загрязнение атмосферы вредными веществами и мероприятия по его сокращению //Экология: вчера, сегодня, завтра. – 2019. – С. 249-252.
37. Glovatsky O. et al. Estimation of the forecast of pump ready rate for reclamation systems //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2021. – Т. 1030. – №. 1. – С. 012115.
38. Ergashev R. et al. Technology of water supply to water inlets of pumping stations //IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering. – IOP Publishing, 2021. – Т. 1030. – №. 1. – С. 012156.
39. Сайдуллаев С. Р., Сатторов А. Б. Ананавий қозонхона ўчоқларида ёқилғи сарфини таҳлил қилиш ва камчиликларини бартараф этиш //Научно-методический журнал "Uz Akademia. – 2020. – С. 198-204.
40. В. И. Калицун Водоотводящие системы и сооружения. Учебник для ВУЗов. –М.: Стройиздат. 1987 г.
41. Ustemirov S. R. U. Solar hot water supply equipment with the help of solar energy //Science and Education. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 245-249.

42. В. С. Дикаревский «Отведение и очистка поверхностных сточных вод» Л. «Стройиздат» 1990 г.
43. Бердиев О. Б., Бозоров И., Парсаева Н. Ж. К оценке напряженно-деформированного состояния конических оболочек //Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 7-2. – С. 48-51.
44. Махмудов И. Э. и др. Гидравлическая модель регулирования колебаний уровня воды в Большом Наманганском канале //Гидротехника. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 52-54.
45. Mahmudov I., Kazakov E. OPERATING CONDITIONS AND RELIABILITY PARAMETERS OF HYDRAULIC ENGINEERING FACILITIES ON THE LARGE NAMANGAN CANAL //Acta of Turin Polytechnic University in Tashkent. – 2020. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 8.
46. Петров А. А., Садиев У. А. Прогнозирование долговечности конструкций ГТС с антикоррозионным и герметизирующим покрытием //Гидротехника. – 2019. – №. 3. – С. 76-77.
47. Садиев У. А. Управление и моделирование в магистральных каналах при изменяющихся значениях гидравлических параметров водного потока //Мелиорация и водное хозяйство. – 2016. – №. 6. – С. 10-11.
48. Махмудов И. Э., Садиев У. Разработка научно-методических мер по повышению эффективности и надежности управления использования водных ресурсов в ирригационных системах (на примере Каршинского магистрального канала) //Водному сотрудничеству стран Центральной Азии-20 лет: опыт прошлого и задачи будущего. – 2013. – С. 141.
49. Sadiev U. A. oth. Modeling of water resource management processes in river basins (on the example of the basin of the Kashkadarya river) //International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology. – 2018. – Т. 5. – С. 5481-5487.
50. Бердиев О. Б. и др. Напряженно-деформированное состояние пологих и подъемистых конических оболочек с учетом влияния краевого эффекта //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 6. – С. 123-126.